

Short communication

FIRST RECORD OF *BELONOCHILUS NUMENIUS* (SAY, 1832) (HEMIPTERA: HETEROPTERA: LYGAEIDAE) FROM MONTENEGRO

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The sycamore seed bug, *Belonochilus numenius* (Say, 1832), is a Nearctic tree specialist indigenous to Canada, USA and Mexico (Wheeler, 1984; Maw *et al.*, 2000). It completes its entire life cycle on the globular fruits of their hostplants, *Platanus* spp. Both nymphs and adults feed on mature and immature fruits, which are also the site where oviposition occurs. This multivoltine species produces up to four generations a year and overwinters in the egg stage; in southern latitudes overwintering adults may be found under tree bark (Wheeler, 1984).

The earliest records in Europe date back to 2008 from Spain (Gessé *et al.*, 2009) and France (Matocq, 2008) and since then its presence was confirmed in 19 European countries. All of the European reports are summarized by Srebrova *et al.* (2019) except the one published from Croatia (Martinović *et al.*, 2019).

In the present paper, the first record of *Belonochilus numenius* (Say, 1832) from Montenegro is reported. The species was observed on 8 October 2020 in Igalo (42.45583585 N, 18.50894424 E, 7 m a.s.l) in an urban area with plane trees, *Platanus* sp. Although these trees are tall, a few seed balls were still accessible for collection, revealing the presence of numerous adult *B. numenius* specimens and mating pairs. A few adults were also found on fallen seed balls lying on the ground. The collected specimens (Fig. 1) are stored in the Heteroptera Collection of the Dubrovnik Natural History Museum (DNHM). Identification was based on morphological characters described in Gessé *et al.* (2009). *B. numenius* is easily distinguishable from the similar *Orsillus* species as it has only one spine on the profemora.

Igalo is close to the border with Croatia and only 40 km aerial distance from Dubrovnik, where the presence of *B. numenius* was reported in the previous year (Martinović *et al.*, 2019). While not being a threat to the hostplant, its impact on the populations of autochthonous insect species that occupy and are dependent on the same ecological niche is still to be investigated (Srebrova *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 1. Adult specimens of *Belonochilus numenius* from Igalo, Montenegro. Left: female; right: male. (photo: Matea Martinović).

References: Gessé, F., Ribes, J. & Goula, M. (2009). *Bulletin of Insectology*, 62: 121-123. Martinović, M., Gjeldum, A. & Koren, T. (2019). *Natura Croatica*, 28(2): 481-484. Matocq, A. (2008). *Bulletin de la Societe Entomologique de France*, 113: 533-534. Maw, H. E. L., Footitt, R. G., Hamilton, K. G. A. & Scudder, G. G. E. (2000). *NRC Research Press*, Ottawa, 220 pp. Srebrova, K., Nacheski, S. & Sotirovski, K. (2019). *Southeast European Forestry*, 10(2): 145-149. Wheeler, A. G. Jr. (1984). *Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington*, 86: 790-796.

ПРВИ НАЛАЗ *BELONOCILUS NUMENIUS* (SAY, 1832)
(HEMIPTERA: HETEROPTERA: LYGAEIDAE) У ЦРНОЈ ГОРИ

МАТЕА МАРТИНОВИЋ

Извод

У раду се износи податак о првом регистровању стенице *Belonochilus numenius* (Say, 1832) у Црној Гори. Пронађена је у приморском месту Игало, у урбаном подручју где расту платани као украсне биљке, на чијим плодовима се ова врста храни и живи.

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